

RESULTS OF APPLICATION OF TRADITIONAL METHODS FOR PREDICTING IMPAIRMENTS OF BONE REGENERATION IN CLOSED FRACTURES OF TUBULAR BONES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10974320>

Rezume

While traditional tests are sensitive to nonspecific wound infections in the early stages after surgery, in the long term they transform into the process of allergization. This can be confirmed by the dynamics of the specificity of LIB, the severity of which increases with the onset of long-term periods of treatment for a fracture of long bones, which indicates the need for a more in-depth study of the immunological aspects of both the cellular and humoral links, which will most likely allow optimizing the method for predicting impaired regeneration of long bone fractures. tubular bones.

Keywords: Closed fracture, tubular bone, prognosis, regeneration

Relevance. It is believed that a violation of bone regeneration in closed fractures of tubular bones, leading to the formation of a false joint, occurs in about 2% of all fractures, but with certain injuries this violation can reach 20% with certain injuries (1,3,5,7,18,20).

The main problems associated with impaired bone regeneration in closed fractures of tubular bones are associated with prolonged pain syndrome, loss of limb function and mental stress conditions. The financial consequences can often be significant for patients due to the loss of potential earnings and estimated medical costs of up to £79,000 per case. Most often, a violation of bone regeneration, leading to the formation of a false joint, occurs with fractures of the bones of the forearm, humerus, tibia, collarbone and femur (2,4,6,8,26).

There is information regarding the controlled role of cytokines in the process of bone tissue regeneration. Specific morphogenetic proteins and cytokines of tumor necrosis factor (in particular β) determine the process of bone regeneration (9,11,13,15,17,22,24).

In all cytokines, bone morphogenetic proteins, which are the largest subfamily of the TGF- β superfamily, are the most commonly used growth factors because they are already present in bone tissue and are reported to be necessary for fetal tissue development and fracture repair. TGF- β itself is also known as an important growth factor in the regulation of osteoblastic and osteoclastic

activity, which is an important process of bone homeostasis and remodeling (10,12,14,16,18,28).

The purpose of the study: to study the results of the application of traditional methods for predicting bone regeneration in patients with closed fractures of tubular bones.

Material and methods. The studies were conducted in patients treated at the Samarkand regional branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period 2017-2019.

The results and their discussion. In patients after extramedullary osteosynthesis in the early postoperative period (1-3 days), ultrasound examination of the fracture zone revealed the presence of interruption of periosteal echoes 2-4 mm in size in the direction of the fracture line. There was swelling of all layers in the soft tissues around the fracture zone, but to a greater extent in subcutaneous fat. Compared with healthy areas of soft tissues, soft tissues in the fracture zone had an intermittent character, which were combined with high and low signals of echogenic path formation. There were no signs of blood accumulation in the fracture zone and in the area of the postoperative wound. The extramedullary structure for osteosynthesis is visualized in full contour, with smooth edges. The presence of small vessels with their different types is traced.

Conclusions.

1. The analysis of visual control of bone regeneration after a fracture allows you to structure the stages of this process. The method is effective for controlling the dynamics of the process. However, the possibilities of this method for forecasting are limited, since the basis of the ongoing regeneration processes is determined by the timing.
2. Analysis of the leukocyte reaction of blood in patients with closed fractures of long tubular bones and in dynamics after osteosynthesis allows us to draw certain conclusions regarding their informational possibilities in predicting violations of bone consolidation. First of all, it should be noted that immune disorders in the body are most pronounced in the early stages after osteosynthesis, especially in patients with purulent-inflammatory complications in the form of suppuration of a postoperative wound and/ or the development of osteomyelitis, which is apparently associated with activation of leukopoiesis.

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